

Paper Title: ***Achieving hot-day take-off with fuel cells through efficient thermal management***

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Hydrogen fuel cell powered aircraft propulsion is one key technology to enable environmentally friendly aviation. Electrically driven and fuel cell powered propulsion systems enable zero in-flight CO₂ emissions. One of the main challenges of fuel cell powered aviation is thermal management and heat rejection. Electrical efficiencies of fuel cells are predicted to reach 50% by 2030. This means each Watt of electricity produced in the fuel cell will generate a Watt of heat that needs to be dissipated. While combustion engines can reject the majority of waste heat through exhaust gases, the heat produced by a fuel cell has to be dissipated via a heat exchanger. The resulting excessive size and air resistance of heat exchangers is a showstopper for hydrogen-electric aircraft.

The Horizon Europe project exFan (101138184) solves this problem by innovating a fuel cell electric aircraft thermal management and recuperation system: The exFan propulsion system applies the Meredith-Effect to produce thrust from waste heat. This has the potential to increase the thermal efficiency of the propulsion system by 8% compared to heat dissipation via a surface heat exchanger that does not add drag. Optimized additively manufactured heat exchangers (HX), novel surface technologies to inhibit fouling of the HX, a thermal management concept that increases the temperature difference as well as highly efficient geared drivetrain configurations are developed to TRL3 to achieve a compact MW-class propulsion system for future fuel cell electric aircraft.

The thermal management system for a fuel cell electric propulsion system has to control the temperature of components with different operating temperatures: Li-Ion batteries can operate at up to 45°C, PEM-fuel cells (PEMFC) at up to 80°C with the gearbox, power electronics and electric machine being able to run at slightly higher temperatures. Due to the low temperature of the heat sources, heat dissipation during take-off on hot days with over 40°C on the tarmac is a major challenge for fuel cell electric aircraft.

This paper outlines the preliminary design process of the thermal management system in exFan. Results for mass, size and energy consumption of three concepts to increase heat quality are presented: (1) LT-PEMFC with a heat pump for the battery cooling circuit to allow heat rejection during high ambient temperatures (2) both LT-PEMFC and battery coolant circuit with a heat pump to increase the heat quality of the largest heat sources up to 300°C and (3) HT-PEMFC with an operating temperature of up to 160°C. The investigation is performed for different power splits of fuel cell and battery with the goal to provide the possibility of hot-day take-off for fuel cell electric aircraft. This research builds on the findings of Link et al. 2023 and Kellermann et al. 2022.

The results of this study are generally applicable for researchers in the fields of hybrid-electric, battery electric and fuel-cell electric aircraft and can be used as a basis for decision making when choosing the architecture of an electric propulsion thermal management system.

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